

Design and Develop a Child Rescue Robot from Borewell

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ABSTRACT:

As we mentioned in our last paper which addressed the problems faced by children who have fallen inside borewells, we now present a solution to these defined problems. Our solution aims to rescue children who have fallen into borewells and to overcome the challenges outlined in our previous paper.

Keywords: spur gears, split-hand end effector, crab handend effector, visual streaming.

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INTRODUCTION

India faces numerous challenges including water scarcity, exacerbated by high resource demand. Bore wells, often used to extract groundwater, are abandoned once demand diminishes, posing serious threats, especially to children. These wells, ranging from 100 to 300 feet deep and 10 to 12 inches in diameter, become dangerous traps. Confined spaces lack oxygen, maintain high temperatures, and plunge into darkness, creating life-threatening conditions. Incidents of children falling into bore wells are not uncommon, with only 30% resulting in successful rescues. Tamil Nadu alone has witnessed ten innocent lives lost over 15 years. Recent cases like Sujith's highlight the urgent need for effective solutions. This project aims to save lives lost in bore wells, stressing innovative equipment and rescue strategies. The objective is to prevent further tragedies and safeguard innocent lives.

LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] Methods to keep child alive in a bore should take in to consideration the lack of oxygen, increased temperature and humidity, which produces hyperthermia. These problems are addressed with fresh air delivery or without delivery of oxygen. The remotely controlled robot will go down the borewell and perform the action.

[2] This paper considers three different cases of weight of children like 12kg, 15kg and 18kg based on which the device was designed.

This study designs the device with the help of night vision camera with torchlight, oxygen pipe with an oxygen cylinder, vacuum pipe and suction cup.

[3] The rescue team tries to approach the victim from a parallel well that take about 20-60 hours to dig. This complicated process makes 70% of the rescue operations fail. The design of handling system is made in such a way that the baby/victim never gets hurt and the robot itself provides some pretreatment to make the baby survive.

[4] Rescue of trapped child from bore well is very risky and difficult process when compared to the other accidents. It takes more than a day to save the child. Here, the child who is stuck inside the hole is to be saved by the clipper which pick and place the child with the help of remote controller.

[5] In this project, a new method has been introduced for a practical, safe, time saving rescue with less manpower. Here the system utilizes the associated work of wireless technology with mechanical setup for the rescue. Various technically efficient gadgets are combined in the setup.

OBJECTIVES

To address these challenges, we have established specific objectives outlined below:

1. To design and implement a mechanism using end effector ensuring the safety.
2. Implement a surveillance system for viewing the child through-out the rescue operation.

To design proper End effector for holding of child with very good grip.

Figure 1. Block Diagram

In addition to the core components, the system is designed with redundancy measures to ensure reliability and safety during rescue operations. Emergency shutdown mechanisms are integrated into the control box to swiftly halt the robot's movements in case of unforeseen circumstances. Continuous monitoring of oxygen levels and motor performance is conducted to pre-emptively address any potential issues and maintain operational efficiency. Regular maintenance schedules are established to uphold the functionality of all equipment and ensure readiness for deployment at any given time. Comprehensive training programs are provided to operators to familiarize them with the system's operation and protocols, enabling swift and effective response during rescue missions. Lastly, ongoing research and development efforts are undertaken to innovate and enhance the system's capabilities, staying at the forefront of rescue technology and maximizing effectiveness in critical situations.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology begins with the critical step of concept selection, where various ideas are evaluated to determine the most viable approach for the project. Following this, a comprehensive literature survey is conducted to gather relevant

information and insights from existing research and developments in the field. With a solid foundation of knowledge established, the next phase involves creating a 3D layout or model, providing a visual representation of the proposed design. This facilitates better understanding and allows for refinement before moving forward. Subsequently, meticulous attention is given to selecting materials that align with the required dimensions and specifications of the project, ensuring optimal performance and functionality. Through careful analysis and calculation, the chosen materials are evaluated to determine their suitability and feasibility for the intended application. Finally, the results obtained from this process are synthesized and presented in the concluding phase, summarizing the findings and implications for future work. This systematic approach ensures a thorough and methodical progression from concept to conclusion, ultimately contributing to the successful realization of the project objectives.

Figure 2. Methodology

The CAD model we've developed represents a meticulous approach to addressing the various challenges encountered during child rescue operations. Careful consideration has been given to factors such as darkness, limited visibility, communication barriers, and the risk of suffocation. Designed with safety as the paramount concern, this model integrates innovative features tailored specifically for effective and secure child rescue. Through advanced engineering and comprehensive planning, we aim to create a reliable and efficient solution that minimizes risks and maximizes success rates in borewell rescue missions.

Fabrication

Figure 3. CNC Laser cutting

During the prototyping phase of this robot, all metal plates and components were meticulously crafted using a CNC laser cutting machine. This advanced technology ensured precise and accurate cuts, allowing for seamless assembly and optimal functionality of the robot. The use of CNC laser cutting not only expedited the manufacturing process but also guaranteed consistency and uniformity in the production of each part. This precision engineering approach contributed to the overall reliability and performance of the robot, meeting the highest standards of quality and craftsmanship.

Solution

The robot is divided into three parts as

- i. Top
- ii. Middle part
- iii. Bottom part.

Figure 4. CAD Model Front View

Figure 5. CAD Model Orthogonal View

The top part contains an air compressor and electronics components, the middle part contains motors to rotate the body and also contains a horizontal extender which is used to extend the distance between the end effector. The bottom part contains the end effectors to grab the child. The machine is constructed using mild steel for the durability with safety major as the problem encountered by us there are two scenarios one is with space availability and without space availability.

For space availability scenario we use split hand mechanism.

Figure 6. Space Availability

During this scenario the robot is equipped with split had mechanism. In the intricate choreography of the rescue mission, every movement is meticulously orchestrated to ensure the safety and well-being of the child trapped underground. As the robotic arms extend horizontally to accommodate the child's size, the split-hand end effector approaches with calculated precision, guided by real-time surveillance feedback. Careful observation of the surrounding environment ensures that no obstacles impede the rescue effort, allowing for smooth and unhindered operation. With a firm yet gentle grip, the split hand envelops the armpit region, providing stability and support as the child is carefully lifted to safety. Throughout the ascent, the robot's sensors continuously monitor vital signs and environmental conditions, providing critical data to the rescue team above ground. As the child emerges into the daylight, a collective sigh of relief echoes through the rescue site, signaling the successful completion of the mission. Amidst the chaos and urgency, the robotic system stands as a beacon of hope and ingenuity, demonstrating the power of technology to save lives in the most challenging of circumstances.

Figure 7. Split Hand Mechanism

In this mechanism the child is grabbed near the arm pit. The both arms or independent of each other. Each arm rotates 60 degrees each and can extended its size horizontally according to the size of the child. When the child is stuck with respect to this senior the robot has to be sent near to the child and see the space available near the arm pit of the child through the surveillance system. After visualizing the space send the split hand end effector near the arm pit. Rotate the split hand grab the whole arm pit of the child. Slowly pull the robot up, disengage the split hand and rescue mission is completed.

Figure 8. CAD Model

For without space availability scenario, we use Crabhand mechanism.

Figure 9. Without Space Availability

During this scenario the robot is equipped with Crab hadmechanism.

In this mechanism the child is grabbed near the Wrist. The both wrist or independent of each other. Each arm rotates 60 degrees each and can extended its size horizontally according to the size of the child. When the child is stuck with respect to this senior the robot has to be sent near to the child and see the space available near the wrist of the child through the surveillance system. After visualizing the space send the crab hand end effector near the wrist. Rotate the crab hand grab to the wrist of

the child. Lock the wrist properly slowly pull the robot up, disengage the crab hand and rescue mission is completed.

monitor the child's condition and movements throughout the operation.

Figure 10. Crab Hand Mechanism

In this mechanism the child is grabbed near the Wrist. The both wrist or independent of each other. Each arm rotates 60 degrees each and can extended its size horizontally according to the size of the child. When the child is stuck with respect to this senior the robot has to be sent near to the child and see the space available near the wrist of the child through the surveillance system. After visualizing the space send the crab hand end effector near the wrist. Rotate the crab hand grab to the wrist of the child. Lock the wrist properly slowly pull the robot up, disengage the crab hand and rescue mission is completed.

Figure 11. CAD Model

Surveillance Camera

The surveillance camera employed in the rescue robot for borewells plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety and effectiveness of the rescue operation. Typically, these cameras are equipped with

high-resolution imaging capabilities and are strategically positioned on the robot to provide comprehensive coverage of the borewell shaft. They offer real-time video feed, allowing rescue personnel to.

The surveillance camera enables continuous observation of the child's location and status, even in low-light or dark conditions, enhancing situational awareness and facilitating informed decision-making. Additionally, the footage captured by the camera can be recorded and analyzed later for debriefing purposes or to improve future rescue strategies.

Overall, the surveillance camera serves as a vital tool in borewell rescue operations, providing valuable visual information to aid in the safe and successful retrieval of trapped individuals.

Figure 12. Video Streaming

Figure 13. Surveillance Camera

RESULT

Figure 14. Crab Hand

Figure 15. Split had

The provided image represents the successful conclusion of our project, achieving the stated objectives. It captures the culmination of our efforts and the fulfilment of our goals. The picture vividly illustrates how we have met the targets set forth at the beginning of our endeavour. It serves as a visual testament to our dedication and hard work throughout the project timeline. Overall, it encapsulates the successful outcome of our collective efforts.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our established objectives aim to address the multifaceted challenges involved in borewell child rescue operations. Through the design and implementation of a mechanism utilizing an end effector, safety is prioritized at every step of the process. Additionally, the integration of a surveillance system ensures continuous monitoring of the child's status throughout the rescue operation, enhancing situational awareness and response capabilities. Furthermore, the development of a proper end effector with a strong grip emphasizes the importance of securely holding the child to mitigate risks and ensure a successful rescue outcome. By adhering to these objectives, we strive to create a robust and effective solution for borewell child rescue scenarios.

In addition to prioritizing safety and implementing surveillance systems, our objectives underscore a commitment to innovation and meticulous design. By developing a mechanism with an end effector specifically tailored for

borewell child rescue, we aim to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in the retrieval process. Furthermore, the emphasis on creating an end effector with a strong grip reflects our dedication to engineering solutions that address the unique challenges posed by these scenarios.

Through these objectives, we not only seek to mitigate risks and ensure the successful rescue of trapped children but also to inspire confidence in our ability to adapt and innovate in the face of adversity. Our relentless pursuit of excellence drives us to continually refine and optimize our approach, ultimately striving to set new standards for borewell child rescue operations and safeguarding the lives of those in need.

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